

What Screening Tools Do Nurses Use to Identify Delirium in Hospitalised Adults?

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List of abbreviations

4AT - the 4'A's test for detecting delirium.

5 P's – pee, pus, pain, poo, pills.

ABCDEF Bundle - Implementation of Delirium Prevention Guidelines. A: Assess, Prevent, and Manage Pain, B: Both Spontaneous Awakening Trials (SATs) and Spontaneous Breathing Trials (SBTs), C: Choice of Analgesia and Sedation, D: Delirium: Assess, Prevent, and Manage, E: Early Mobility and Exercise, F: Family Engagement and Empowerment.

ADL - Assessment of Activities of Daily Living.

CAM - Confusion Assessment Method.

CAM-ICU - confusion assessment method for the intensive care

unit. CHART-DEL – chart-based Delirium Identification Instrument.

CIWA - Clinical Institute for Withdrawal Assessment of

Alcohol. DEAR – Delirium Elderly At Risk.

DI - The Delirium Index.

DOSS – Delirium Observation Screening Scale.

DRS – Delirium Rating Scale.

DSM – The Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental

Illnesses. EBHC – Evidence-Based Health Collection.

HELP - Hospital Elder Life Program.

HMIC – The Healthcare Management Information Consortium.

ICDSC - intensive care delirium screening checklist.

ICU – Intensive Care Unit.

GSC - The Glasgow Coma Scoring System.

KT – Knowledge transfer.

MDAS - Memorial delirium assessment scale.

Mini-Cog - Mini-Cognitive Assessment Tool.

MMED – multi-modality event dataset.

MMSE - Mini Mental Status Examination.

MoCA - Montreal Cognitive Assessment.

NDKA - Nurse's Delirium Knowledge Assessment.

NEWS - National Early Warning Score.

NHS – National Health Service.

NICE - the National Institute for Health Care and Excellence.

Nu-DESC – Nursing Delirium Screening Scale.

PEO – Population, Environment/Exposure, Outcome.

PINCHME – Pain, Infection, Nutrition, Constipation, Hydration, Medication, Environment.

POD – Post Operative Delirium.

PRISMA – Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and

Meta-Analyses. RADAR – Recognising Active Delirium As a Routine.

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RASS - Richmond Agitation Sedation Scale.

RN – Registered Nurse.

SPIDER – Sample, Phenomenon of Interest, Design, Evaluation, Research

type. SPMSQ - Short Portable Mental Status Questionnaire.

SQID - single question in delirium.

TDF - Theoretical Domains Framework.

UK – United Kingdom.

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Abstract

Delirium is a clinical syndrome characterised by altered consciousness and cognitive function, which remains poorly understood. Some nurses felt confident in identifying delirium without the aid of a tool it, but research shows nurses often fail to identify delirium, which is undetected in 30% to 75% of cases. Nurses detected delirium accurately only in 25% of cases, often misinterpreting symptoms.

NICE provides guidance on recognising and managing delirium. The literature search revealed several screening tools validated for nurses. Further investigation highlighted that most of those tools were all developed from one source, so how do they differ, and why were they developed?

Some of the tools have been adapted for intensive care settings and are believed to enhance patient evaluations. Others use a score-based model for assessing delirium severity.

The tools vary in application time, from around 15 minutes, down to just one minute to complete. One even states it takes only 7 seconds.

Several screening tools are in use, but limited literature is available for some tools. Some of the tools claim to have proven reliable and valid, being available in multiple languages for use in various countries, saying they achieved a delirium identification accuracy of 97.6%.

Many tools have been updated since their creation to newer versions, yet studies reveal many barriers to effective screening. Regular screening is crucial for improving patient care.

Introduction

When looking at the origin of delirium, Koizia et al provide the information that “delirium is defined as a clinical syndrome characterised by disturbed consciousness, cognitive function or perception, which has an acute onset and fluctuating course” (2019: 228). While research has increased knowledge and

treatment, Miranda et al explain “the pathophysiology of delirium is still insufficiently understood” (2018: 2)

Ali et al explain “The word delirium is derived from Latin words *de* (away from, out of) and *lira* (the earth thrown up between two furrows)” (2011: 25). They continue by explaining its use is “to describe a condition in which an individual is performing at a lower level than normal and is not at the top of his or her conscious level” (2011: 25). This is expanded on, by El Hussein, Hirst, and Salyers, who say “it has been further defined as an acute confusional state, acute brain syndrome, acute cerebral insufficiency and toxic-metabolic encephalopathy” (2015: 907).

Bergeron et al advice using the DSM-IV, “delirium, usually described as an acute reversible state, is a psychiatric diagnosis with specific criteria” (2001: 859) (appendix 1).

Since then, an updated version of the DSM has been published, with Kalish, Gillham, and Unwin, (2014) advising adjustments to the original criteria to encompass a more detailed explanation of the potential causes. Also, a new section was added, together with the updates, which should aid clinical staff in determining delirium, even if other conditions may trigger similar symptoms (appendix 2).

Marcantonio explains, “delirium affects more than one-third of hospitalised elderly patients. Yet, it remains under-recognised and is often inappropriately evaluated and managed” (2008: 42). The importance of this is discussed by Schreier, who described risk factors (appendix 3), effects, and experiences for

patients by saying “emotional distress occurs” (2010: 177), continuing to explain that post recovery patients “were able to recall experiencing hallucinations (auditory, tactile, and visual), psychomotor agitation, and disorientation to time and place” (2010: 177). With NHS inform advising, “after recovering from delirium, there’s an increased risk of dementia. People living with dementia who develop delirium may be worse after delirium”. Continuing to explain, “people who have experienced distress during delirium may develop post-traumatic stress symptoms. This includes intrusive memories of delirium and symptoms of anxiety and depression” (2024. 11).

El Hussein, Hirst and Salyers (2015) and Miranda et al (2018) explain that delirium is the most likely complication that an older adult is at risk of developing while hospitalised in any inpatient setting, and there is consistent evidence that delirium is often a result of another underlying condition, but that often nurses do not recognise delirium in their patients irrespective of its severity, suggesting this leads to it remaining undiagnosed in many cases. This is coupled with nurses exhibiting a reluctance to utilise available screening tools, either due to high workloads, lack of training, or in some cases, the misplaced belief that the symptoms presenting represent part of normal cognitive decline associated with age, dementia, or depression.

Blevins and Degennaro highlight the “under-recognition of delirium by health care professionals is an extensive problem: Delirium is estimated to be undetected in 30% to 75% of cases” (2018: 271). They continue to explain that the inadequate

knowledge of nurses, regarding delirium manifestation and associated risk factors, is further complicated by the fluctuating and varied presentation of delirium symptoms.

Haslam-Larmer and Vellani (2024) add to this by advising of the common pitfalls in delirium scoring being a result of the transient and fluctuating symptom presentation and severity, causing missed symptoms if assessment is conducted only once per shift.

Ozsaban and Acaroglu (2016) and Blevins and DeGennaro (2018) both agree, highlighting a knowledge deficit regarding delirium, reporting that a significant difference in delirium assessment rates was found in nurses who perceived delirium as a syndrome that embodies serious problems.

Scott, McIlveney and Mallice (2013) expand on this in their findings, expressing only 54% of nurses involved in their research believe that delirium is a serious problem. This resulted in only 6% of those nurses considering screening for it and 69% believing it was not necessary to monitor for delirium as routine.

Satyapriya et al (2016) provide some factors which may precipitate the development of delirium (appendix 4), but these are far from the complete picture.

In the recognition, diagnosis, and treatment of delirium, NICE (2023) provides advice and guidance on the ailments that increase the likelihood of development, the symptoms to be aware of, and the tools that should be used. (appendix 5). This clinical guideline has evolved throughout delirium detection and treatment to offer

clinicians the best available evidence on diagnosing and managing the condition.

NICE (2023) suggests a combination of tools be used to make an assessment and

diagnosis. They begin with advising daily screening using the SQiD tool, offering the rationale that this tool may aid clinicians in noticing changes from the patients' baseline, which may be an indicator of delirium (Appendix 6). NICE (2023) continues to advise that once there is a positive indication of delirium with the daily screening tools, the clinician should complete a more detailed delirium assessment to aid in a positive diagnosis.

Rice and Castex (2013) explain The American Delirium Society offer specific recommendations for improving the screening for delirium risk, which allows for individualised care of those at risk of delirium, improving the prevention of delirium.

Varghese et al (2014) propose that, as nurses spend more time with patients than physicians do, with appropriate training and education, nurses are crucial in the early recognition, management, and treatment of delirium.

Having encountered patients with potential delirium throughout years of study, and seen staff of all levels, make assumptions that the symptoms presenting which relate to delirium, are more likely part of another condition, e.g. dementia, or medication side effects, and so not seen as important or new and so not documenting them either as delirium or sometimes at all, and so failing to complete screening and follow delirium guidance, the query began to develop, of how nurses are aided in this recognition, or if it is down to clinical judgement. This triggered the thought process of wanting to know more about delirium generally, and how nurses identify and manage the condition.

Search Strategy

Before undertaking a systematic search, some scoping research was completed to check the likelihood of enough literature being available for a systematic search.

The scoping research highlighted various tools which have been developed for use in delirium, or which are not delirium based but may be used alongside a dedicated tool to help, but with a secondary theme of nurses making clinical judgement to not use the tools or not finding value in them.

Combining the gathered information and using the acronym table of PEO (Appendix 7), for the areas of interest, led to the development of the question, “What screening tools do nurses use to identify delirium in hospitalised adults”?

With this research came the realisation that, assessing the methods used by nurses to identify delirium, is needed to identify any gaps in these methods which are leading to the signs of delirium being missed. To best achieve this, a systematic literature review was performed. The rationale for performing a systematic literature review is explained by Aveyard and Sharp, who say “they aim to summarise all the available literature on a topic”, adding “this is the name given to a very detailed review of literature on a topic” (2017:63). This allows the researcher to gather the most complete and relevant literature on a topic allowing the highlighting of any key areas which appear to be missing and so aim to address this.

Aveyard and Sharp (2017) offer the guidance that for research on a topic to be useful in aiding the development of clinical practice, it needs to be relevant primary research, allowing the development of evidence-based practice. Accessing this type of research allows for a critical appraisal of the gathered research, enabling it to be judged for relevance. To aid in this process they provide 6 questions of critical thinking (figure 1) which each result, is analysed using.

6 Questions of Critical Thinking	Explanation
What is it?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What type of evidence is it? For example, is it a literature review, a research study, guidelines, personal opinion, a discussion paper, a website, or another type of evidence? • What are the findings/results or key points and are they relevant to what you want to know?
Where did you find it?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Did you just 'come across' it? Who told you? Or did you access it through a systematic search using a professional database?
Who wrote/said this?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Is it an individual representing their own viewpoint, or an individual/group representing an organisation? • Are they experts on the topic? How do you know?
When was it written/said	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Older key information may still be valid, but you need to check if there has been more recent work.
Why was it written/ said?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Who is the information aimed at – public, professionals, patient/client groups? • What could be the aim of the information? • Could there be a hidden agenda? • Could there be any bias? How do you know?
How do you know if it is good quality?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How have the authors come to their conclusions? • Are the research methods used and/or line of reasoning logical, robust, and understandable? • Are there any flaws in the authors' arguments or approach?

Aveyard and Sharp (2017: 151-152).

Figure 1

To gather literature of an appropriate level, once the question had been developed, the individual parts of the question were deconstructed into their key constituent baseline words. This aided in the formulation of the terms in the SPIDER template (Appendix 8), which would be used to develop the terms used for searching the databases. These words were then assessed to build a complete picture of the

keywords and synonyms, including any appropriate variations in spelling, terminology, and abbreviation words different to the originals but having a similar or the same meaning, and this was maximised with the use of truncation and wildcards.

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These words were then inputted into the chosen databases using the Boolean operator OR: to broaden the search of similar words, and the results of those searches were combined using the Boolean operator AND to narrow the search by combining those results into a more comprehensive and relevant result.

The literature search was performed in stages. The databases CINHAL, COCHRANE, MEDLINE Ovid, HMIC, EMBASE, BRITISH NURSING INDEX, and EBHC were chosen to input the search terms into. The rationale for the use of those databases chosen was their designation of relevance to the field of practice being investigated, which allowed the likelihood of increased relevance of results, along with the ability to provide the most comprehensive access to reliable and consistent literature results of a high-quality, which have a clear, relevant, up-to-date evidence base and in which the literature has been peer-reviewed by appropriate experts for validity, reliability, consistency, and quality of the scientific research reported before the papers publishing. Each of the databases offers its own justification for using it as a relevant place to research (Figure 2)

Database Name	Database justification rationale	Website available at
CINAHL Database	CINAHL includes rigorous curation and indexing of open-access (OA) journals, which has resulted in a growing collection of 1,389 active global OA journals. Once validated and certified for inclusion, these OA journals are treated with high-quality subject indexing and sophisticated, precise/accurate full-text linking.	https://www.ebsco.com/products/research-databases/cinahl-database
Cochrane	The Cochrane Library is one of the strongest sources of health-evidence for nurses. Cochrane articles are very comprehensive and based on the best available evidence.	https://www.cochrane.org/news/cochrane-practice-nursing:-start-the%20Cochrane%20Library%20in%20new-mary%20system%20review%20from%20Cochrane
PubMed	PUBMED is the National Library of Medicine's (NLM) premier bibliographic database that contains references to journal articles in life sciences, with a concentration on biomedicine.	https://www.nlm.nih.gov/medline/medline_home.html#:~:text=REDLINE%20is%20the%20National%20Library,for%20more%20information%20about%20REDLINE
HMIC	Brings together the bibliographic database of two UK health and social care management organisations: the Department of Health's Library and Information Services (DH Data) and King's Fund Information and Library Service. This Health Management and Policy Database, from The Healthcare Management Information Consortium (HMIC), is an invaluable source of information for health-care administrators and managers. DH Data is the database of the Department of Health's Library and Information Services and contains in excess of 174,000 records relating to health and social care management information. Coverage includes official publications, journal articles and grey literature on: health service policy, management and administration, with an emphasis on the British National Health Service; the quality of health services including hospitals, nursing, primary care and public health; the planning, design, construction and maintenance of health service buildings; occupational health; control and regulation of medicines; medical equipment and supplies, and social care and personal-social services	https://www.wobensit.com/en/solutions/health-cmhc-database-36#:~:text=Brings%20together%20the%20bibliographic%20database,of%20the%20records%20have%20abstracts
EMBASE	Embase guides you in using the PICO method in a search. And you can quickly formulate an advanced query to explore deeply indexed content.	https://www.utswest.com/products/embase
British Nursing Index	The British Nursing Index (BNI) is a bibliographic database that indexes articles from the most popular English language nursing journals published primarily in the UK. BNI is a comprehensive index covering all aspects of nursing, midwifery and community healthcare from 1985 to the present.	https://www.utswest.com/uk/products/british-nursing-index#:~:text=The%20British%20Nursing%20Index%20is%20the,from%201985%20to%20the%20present
EBHC	Evidence-Based Health Collection (EBHC) brings together a useful and distinct collection of evidence-based content resources to provide clinicians, students and researchers access to the best available scientific information to guide clinical decisions and patient care.	https://www.wobensit.com/en/solutions/ebc/evidence-based-health-collection-16002

Figure 2
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As Aveyard and Sharp advice on the process of evidence evaluation, stating, “research can be ranked in order of importance” (2017: 96); a limitation of 25 years was placed on the search regarding publication date. This limitation was important as all primary research showed the majority of screening tools in use, and with sufficient evidence available, had been developed since 1990, so allowing the compilation of the most complete set of results available on the chosen websites, However, as delirium can affect any age, to limit result relevance, a limitation was placed regarding age with the requirement of subjects being aged eighteen years or older, allowing the compilation of a more complete group of results from which to gather the required information and evidence, but removing the likelihood of those results being excessive due to an overly broad age range.

Some of the databases provided results from a global network of literature maximising the evidence gathered, whereas other database results were based solely on literature from the UK which increased the likelihood of the results gathered being relevant to British healthcare practices, so aiding in any potential future patient care or decision-making process based on the relevance of the results gathered. No

geographical restrictions were set on the search as many of the tools are used worldwide and so any adjustments made to them by other countries could be of valuable insight to recommendations made for the UK.

In many cases, the databases offered advanced features in the search function allowing searches to be combined and narrowed increasing the likelihood of relevance of results, and some of the databases provided full access to the high quality resources gathered.

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Other databases were initially searched, but removed, as the literature provided was not relevant or they did not provide full access to the literature meaning some of the results were unavailable for retrieval and reducing the numbers for assessment, or even when abstracts appeared useful, the full-access resources were not in English.

Once all the databases had been searched on December 19th, 2024, the initial result numbers were compiled, totalling 9585. These results and the remaining numbers following each stage of literature assessment were collated using the PRISMA tool, figure 3

Source: Page MJ, et al. BMJ 2021;372:e71. doi: 10.1136/bmj.e71

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Figure 3

with the final number of pieces of literature being retrieved for use in the dissertation amounting to 50 papers and 1 book.

Once these papers were all collected, the process began of reading through them, to identify the key themes related to the question, which allowed the development of the findings.

Findings

Within the papers found during the literature search were a selection of screening tools, which had been researched, developed, and validated for use by nurses in clinical settings. Amongst these are specific tools recommended by NICE clinical guidelines. The assessment tools highlighted by NICE (2023) are the 4AT, the CAM-ICU, or the ICDSC, (which was developed from the CAM-ICU). These are suggested if the patient is post-operative, or in intensive care (appendix 9), due to their development specifically for use in that area of health care.

While not actually a validated delirium screening tool, and so not a direct recommendation, NICE suggests that “some simple tools like the Single Question to Identify Delirium (SQiD) might be useful to help practitioners notice any changes” (2023: 18).

Using this information and the literature gathered allowed an analysis of many of the screening tools available, and how these tools and recommendations have changed as the understanding of delirium and its treatment has progressed. As well as this, the literature provided information on the beliefs and views of some nurses about delirium and its recognition or the use of screening tools.

Available screening Tools.

SQiD

Sands et al (2010) provide an overview of the SQiD tool (appendix 10) and how it is one question asked of the friend or relative of the patient. They explain the SQiD’s use in delirium detection, saying “the diagnosis of delirium is often missed.

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There is an urgent need to find practical methods of improving delirium detection” (2010: 561). In their study, they continue to highlight some evidence suggesting 69% of delirium episodes were missed.

Tieges, Lowrey and MacLulich, speaking about clinical guidelines, advise “the SQiD was included because it has potential utility in non-specialist settings, either on its own or in combination with another assessment tool such as the 4AT if the SQiD is positive” (2021: 1294). Sands et al (2010) theorise that the design of the SQiD is

easier for clinicians to implement during a shift than longer screening tools, and without direct input from the patient themselves. Sands et al (2010) offer research evidence of the sensitivity of SQiD being 80% with a specificity of 71%, which they chart as in close agreement with other delirium detection tools (appendix 11), while highlighting the intention for use of the tool to complement other validated methods, not replace them.

4AT

The 4AT, as described by MacLulich et al (2019), is a screening tool which focuses on four areas of a patient's health to determine any deterioration in their neurological functioning. MacLulich et al offer further information stating, "the 4AT can provide a useful means of providing a consistent approach to screening, especially in busy environments where speed and practicality are important" (2019: 67)

MacLulich et al, (2019) advise the reliability of the 4AT to correctly determine when a patient does not have delirium. They advise the 4AT's high level of specificity at 95% and sensitivity of 76% and state the 4AT's increased distribution into routine clinical use, both resulting from its effective ability to detect delirium when other screening tools may miss it, and due to its ease of use for clinical staff.

Rajeev, Railton and Devalia (2022) provide further information on the 4AT (appendix 12), advising the times a patient may be at increased risk of developing delirium, those being age, a history of previous delirium or mental health problem, and having undergone surgery, specifically long surgeries like joint repairs.

MacLulich et al (2019) speak about the size and speed of using the 4AT in practice compared to previous tests and how this shortened nature creates a speed of use making it beneficial in integrating the 4AT into daily nursing practice.

CAM

Shi et al (2014) and Kong et al (2022) both provide information about the CAM, explaining the four clinical criteria the algorithm utilises, and that a definition of confirmed delirium requires the presence of at least three of these criteria, including that specifically the first two must both be present. They continue explaining that the CAM is one of the tools most frequently used to detect delirium in healthcare.

This agrees with Koizia et al., who advise that “the confusion assessment method (CAM) is a quick, accurate and frequently used tool to recognise and diagnose delirium. It can be incorporated into routine assessment of patients and has been shown to have high sensitivity, specificity, and interrater reliability” (2019: 230).

But it is important to note that this paper's research excluded the intensive care unit, and as the CAM-ICU, is currently recommended by NICE (2010), this could alter the results gathered.

However, in comparison to this, Sands et al, while conducting a study about the SQiD, stated “our study showed the CAM had only 40% sensitivity in the hands of minimally trained clinical staff” (2010: 564). It is, however, important to note that the study by Sands et al was completed in 2010, and as the research by Koizia et al is more recent, this may account for the differing findings.

Rice and Castex (2013) advise that this is one of the most widely used tools to aid in the assessment of confusion. This is partially because it is simple to use and does not require substantial amounts of time to complete. Hosie et al (2015), El Hussein, Hirst and Salyers (2015) and Haslam-Larmer and Vellani (2024), concur with this opinion, advising that the CAM has undergone various validation studies, which have confirmed the validity of its results, and that research indicates nurses showed improved screening and recognition of delirium. Haslam-Larmer and Vellani (2024), continue by advising “completing the CAM takes less than 5 min and can be integrated into routine bedside evaluations” (2024: 2). El Hussein, Hirst and Salyers continue by referring to two papers they reviewed when saying, “CAM is currently considered the gold standard for delirium recognition.” (2015: 910).

Ali et al (2011) and Varghese et al (2014) also offer validity and beneficial results from the CAM, with both expressing the algorithm's simplicity and ease-of-use as a bedside assessment. Both advise that the algorithm has a sensitivity of 94-100%. Varghese et al (2014) continue, by including the information that a mental health background is not required for using this algorithm, but that there is benefit from increased training sessions on delirium. While advocating increased training sessions, they do highlight some research they completed, suggesting that more experienced nurses may potentially show reluctance to change to newer methods of screening for delirium.

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Hosie et al (2015), suggest the potential to create simpler, shorter, and less clinical versions of the CAM, which may be utilised by the family of delirium sufferers to monitor the condition. This could be out of an inpatient environment, or even at a patient's bedside during visits. This holds potential clinical benefits due to the

fluctuating nature of delirium and the fact that family and friends are best placed to notice changes from the patient's baseline.

El Hussein, Hirst, and Salyers (2014) express the view that education on this and similar tools would be generally beneficial to nurses. They felt this would be positive because the results of the study they conducted appear to indicate the CAM as beneficial in recognising delirium. Included in this is a reduction of misdiagnosed delirium when the CAM is utilised.

Haslam-Larmer and Vellani (2024) express that while use of tools like the CAM can be beneficial, they state the importance of detailed, concise documentation of the results in the patient's record, including a detailed description of symptom presentation to allow fellow clinicians to assess changes during subsequent assessments and allowing for prompt treatment to begin.

By comparison Rice and Castex (2013) stated that in the research they conducted, even when the symptoms of delirium had been observed and documented, the nurses using the CAM only accurately detected the presence of delirium in 25% of the patients, often appearing to disregard the symptoms as those of the normal cognitive aging process or as a result of medication the patient was taking. This observation was also highlighted by El Hussein, Hirst, and Salyers (2014), who expressed that “the recognition of delirium is complicated by the fact that delirium continues to be attributed to normal ageing or misdiagnosed by

physicians as dementia or depression” (2014: 907). They highlighted the need for increased education on delirium to combat these issues. Failure to provide the required training for this is likely to lead to reduced delirium detection or

misinterpretation across the board, leading to increased levels of more severe delirium and consequently a poorer outcome for patients.

In their paper El Hussein, Hirst, and Salyers (2014) explain that in their research, “subjective assessments of delirium by RN’s (n = 147) were compared to medical students” (2014: 911). They report an increase in rates of detection of delirium by a group of medical students included in the research, however they continue to advise rather than the likelihood of being an increased affinity with the CAM, this increase may be because of extra training sessions the medical students had completed and so cannot be viewed as a reliable comparison. They offer the opinion that the CAM is better placed for delirium detection when used alongside another approach to help with increased validity. One factor which supports this need is that the study highlights a lack of confidence using the CAM by nurses and that they may require specific training in its implementation and how to interpret the results correctly. This limitation is noted by El Hussein, Hirst, and Salyers (2014), who explain in their research the finding that, during the study period, nurses were able to accurately identify delirium in only 6% of patients. El Hussein, Hirst and Salyers highlight “considering the fluctuating nature of delirium, it is unclear from the study whether all cases were identified” (2014: 908). However, as the study data was not blinded and the nurses involved were aware of the research being conducted, they may have influenced their reporting and thus distorted the results. As well as this, as this study was only conducted at one surgical ICU, it may not have validity

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outside this environment. Also, there is no clarification on whether these 6% were the only patients subsequently diagnosed with delirium.

Another limitation of the CAM is expressed by Schreier (2010), who says use of the CAM is hindered due to the differing computer systems used throughout the various areas of healthcare, and that access to a computer is not always possible at the point of need. These factors may reduce its routine use in practice.

While this information is quite dated in research terms, and globally computer systems have become more common and used in healthcare more often, Tieges, Lowrey and MacLulich offer similar results from 154 NHS trusts, stating “the 4AT’s was the most widely used delirium assessment tool, with 117/146 (80%) of units reporting use; the confusion assessment method was reportedly used in 65/146 (45%) of units and the SQiD in 52/146 (36%) of units” (2021: 1293). There are similar barriers to standard use in practice also mentioned by Hosie et al (2015) who offer the opinion that for the CAM to truly be effective in practice, staff need to be given the time to complete it regularly enough, and the appropriate level of training to implement it with confidence and a high enough standard of sensitivity.

Varghese et al (2014) explain that they collected data from a shorter version of the CAM they created for the study. However, as this adjustment to a shorter version has not been validated, the change of the questionnaire from its original form may also negatively impact the validity of results gathered.

Since the implementation of the CAM into widespread use, it has been superseded as the primary screening tool advised by NICE (2023) but has also been adapted for primary use in intensive care, with the introduction of the CAM-ICU.

Alaterre et al (2023) explain that during the development of the CAM-ICU, physicians' assessments were utilised as a comparison reference for delirium. However, they continue to explain reports showing no difference in sensitivity between assessments completed by nurses compared to those of physicians, offering the opinion that the CAM-ICU's ease of use indicates likely accurate recognition of delirium irrespective of assessor.

Miranda et al explain the development of the CAM-ICU (appendix 13) from the original longer CAM, advising "the confusion assessment method for the intensive care unit (CAM-ICU) is a tool recommended by the clinical guidelines, and is widely used in research and clinical settings" (2018: 1). The CAM-ICU is described by Miranda et al (2018) as, a shorter version of delirium diagnosis, developed from the CAM, which can be administered by any clinical staff member with the correct level of training, and which does not require direct engagement from the patient so making it eligible for use in intubated patients.

Scott, McIlveney and Mallice (2013) speak of the rigorous validity and development evaluating the CAM-ICU has had during its development, ensuring its place in the list of established delirium screening tools in current use. Advice on the development is provided by Meghani and Timmins, who further advise the reduction in administration time by saying "it takes less than 2 min to perform an assessment and is recommended to use twice a shift and repeat if required" (2024: 944).

The impact this has on nurses is highlighted by Haslam-Larmer and Vellani (2024), who offer the opinion that most nurses in their research found the CAM-ICU easy to administer and felt confident in using the tool, believing it would lead to a more comprehensive patient assessment. This has been further developed as Krewulak et al (2020) advise that, since the development of the CAM-ICU, further additions have been implemented, including the CAM-ICU7, which utilises a score based model of delirium severity scoring.

Miranda et al explain it was developed because “the need for a useful and efficient tool for diagnosis of delirium in the ICU has become more widespread” (2018: 1). Miranda et al (2018) advise the shorter nature of the CAM-ICU allows swifter application, increasing the ability for it to be implemented multiple times a day increasing the likelihood of catching episodes of fluctuating delirium.

Despite the CAM-ICU being a tool NICE advise the use of, and which has been translated for use in multiple countries, Miranda et al highlight, “the information available in the medical literature about the diagnostic accuracy of CAM-ICU is highly heterogeneous and ambiguous” (2018: 4).

In contrast to this, Ramaurthy and Scharre state “the CAM-ICU had reasonable results, with a sensitivity and specificity of 81% and 98%” (2022: 255).

Ozsaban and Acaroglu state that when using CAM-ICU “the majority of nurses (76.7%) identified delirium in patients on mechanical ventilation” (2016: 274). They continue by recommending that patients who are admitted to the ICU would benefit from a minimum routine daily screening to address the increased prevalence of delirium in ICU patients, along with the fluctuating nature of delirium.

Conversely, considering the CAM-ICU's development for patients in the ICU, Varghese et al (2014) reported a high burden while caring for patients with delirium, with only 3% of critical care nurses from 232 defining delirium as an important condition to consistently evaluate. They continue, while speaking about a training programme they were assessing, with the observation of a potential negative relationship between clinical experience and willingness to change to more up-to-date screening methods. However, after making this observation, Varghese et al (2014) state no difference in score between the groups assessed.

One of the studies Blevins and Degennaro (2018) reviewed, suggested nurses deemed delirium a significant issue yet believed delirium screening was not necessary. This raises the question of why a nurse who deems delirium a significant issue, would also consider screening for it unnecessary. Possibly, the screening is currently being completed by the doctors in that area of practice, leaving the nurse reluctant to potentially duplicate the screening. They continue with the advice that, being a fundamental part of delirium recognition, CAM-ICU requires strategies to incorporate its training into daily practice. As these strategies may take time to implement, this could lead to further loss of recognition due to a lack of compliance.

Alaterre et al (2023) offer some criticism to the CAM-ICU, advising that its result "is binary: it is 'positive' = delirium is present or 'negative' = delirium is absent" (2023: 6).

This is also noted by Van Rompaey et al (2008) who comment on the singular time frame assessed and the inflexibility of the CAM-ICU's screening compared to the

NEECHAM delirium screening tool (appendix 14). This also has the effect of causing other barriers for the nurse screening with the CAM-ICU. Due to its inflexibility, Scott,

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Mcllveney and Mallice (2013) report on nurses struggling to recognise the delirium subtypes in sedated patients, highlighting three barriers most often encountered (appendix 15). However, it is questionable how transferable into general practice these findings are with the results being gathered only within one single UK critical care unit. Most of the other screening tools available appear to be based on the original CAM or the CAM-ICU.

ICDSC

In their study, Bergeron et al, explain the ICDSC tool which was developed from the CAM alongside the CAM-ICU, describing the 8 stage tool and scoring system, which is user-friendly and can be used with ease at a patient's bedside, was developed and how "the first four screening elements refer directly to the first two DSM-IV criteria" (2001: 859). Bergeron et al (2001) continue, with an explanation that the IDCSC during their study showed a sensitivity of 99%. Bergeron et al conclude with the statement "the speed with which the questionnaire can be completed, as well as the fact that many items can be evaluated by a nurse in the course of routine evaluation, make it practical in the current climate of cost-cutting and maximal efficiency" (2001: 863).

Krewulak et al (2020) agree with this statement, explaining that the IDCSC is a validated screening tool in everyday use currently and is completed by staff twice a day, allowing a score to be developed for that patient over the course of a 12-hour

period.

Mohseni Moallem Kolaci, Ayatollahi and Elyasi (2021), and Meghani and Timmins (2024) comment that the ICDSC is one of the most widely used screening

tools for delirium, which has been validated and assessed as reliable and whose design allows it to be utilised on a range of patients, including those who are intubated, while continuing to express the rigour of the ICDSC's development and how this has positively impacted its results and validity.

This opinion is disagreed with by Mohseni Moallem Kolaci, Ayatollahi and Elyasi (2020), who advise the inability of the ICDSC to be used on unconscious or drowsy patients, due to the score being based on the condition of that patient's engagement.

Ozsaban and Acaroglu (2015) regarding this screening tool, offer the information that it is not a tool widely used in Turkish ICU's even though they agree that its reliability and validity have been proven. While the authors do not offer a reason for this in their paper, it may potentially be caused by a lack of knowledge. This is confirmed by Meghani and Timmins, who also criticise the tool, stating "more than half of the nurses 66% have never heard about the ICDSC scale" (2024: 947).

El Hussein, Hirst, and Salyers (2014) highlight concurring evidence with previous studies regarding educational programmes or tools designed for the detection of delirium, boosting nurses' ability to recognise delirium. This is highlighted further in the literature by Scott, McIlveney and Mallice (2013), who explain the ease of use and minimal time scale needed for implementation of the approach, and how this lends itself to use by staff who have not undergone specific training in how to use the tool.

Fraser et al (2018) report that nurses approached during their research showed an increase, to 93% in nurses reporting plans to utilise the tool in following shifts. In their research, the percentage of nurses performing the ICDSC did not change, which suggests that while it may have increased knowledge of the

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approach's existence to staff, it did not appear to influence the nurses' likelihood of completing it, moving forward. However, they did document a split between completion concordance between shifts, with night shift nurses being only 5% more likely to complete it than those on an evening shift, but 20.7% more likely than nurses on a day shift. Fraser et al suggested "less experienced nurses who often work in the night and evening shifts may have relied more heavily on the tool than experienced nurses" (2018: 42) (appendix 16). While not specified in the literature, this potentially suggests lack of concordance may relate to experience gaps or relate to workload on the shifts in question and nurses feeling they need to prioritise other tasks deemed more important.

Also, as the engagement with the researchers was voluntary, this may reduce the validity of the results, as nurses with limited delirium training may have declined to engage. This can potentially be seen in the fact that only 24 nurses engaged out of 47 eligible to engage, which is a small number to base conclusive findings on.

Further evidence of potential selection bias can be seen when noting that the nurses who consented to participate in the research received financial compensation; this may have encouraged a lean towards the desired result to ensure the results presented would be included in the final paper. The literature result also showed a result far lower than that of other literature, suggesting it may imply an increased level of delirium prevention. However, it also may suggest misinterpretation of

symptoms or failure to document correctly; without proper investigation, this would leave the results gathered possibly invalidated.

Krewulak et al (2021) explain the results gathered in their research setting, offering the guidance that the ICDSC and their comparator tool only showed fair concordance. However, these results may lack validity as scores in a research

setting may not be comparable with the scores the tools would show in clinical settings and so should be used with caution. They suggest that, compared to other tools, the focus of the ICDSC is to record disruption to the patient's sleep-wake cycle.

Krewulak et al (2020) suggest the ICDSC offers benefits if used with other delirium tools to help confirm symptoms and, as a result, improve the accuracy of any diagnosis. Krewulak et al suggest that any increase in delirium detection using the ICDSC may result from its application “calculated from bedside registered nurses observations of the patient” (2020: 11), and that symptoms can be recorded at differing times, whereas other tools for example “the CAM-ICU-7 is a point in time assessment of the patients mentation” (2020: 11).

Even though most of the literature offers guidance on the ICDSC being able to be done in stages, capturing a wider potential array of delirium symptoms, Van Rompaey et al (2008) in their comparative study, explain that the ICDSC was performed during their research only once a day by a trained technician. As highlighted by Bergeron et al (2001), due to the design of the ICDSC being to capture symptoms presenting within the last 8 to 12 hours, and the known fluctuating nature of delirium, this once-a-day approach risks missing the development, progression or cessation of symptoms throughout the remainder of the day or night.

Mohseni Moallem Kolaci, Ayatollahi, and Elyasi (2021) express similar views, highlighting the simplicity of its use and how this aids in swifter recognition of potential delirium, so benefiting the patients, even those who are unable to verbally communicate. They advise the ability of the ICDSC to capture the symptoms of delirium, even though they may fluctuate over time and how it is a tool used and

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agreed upon by a variety of healthcare professionals, including nurses and psychiatrists.

In contrast to this, El Hussein, Hirst, and Salyers (2014) suggest that while the application of approaches including the ICDSC can offer significant benefits, it is fundamental to provide training in its use to all staff performing screening. This expression of need for training directly contradicts the opinions offering its swiftness and ease of use. However, as with the CAM, mandatory training would potentially be beneficial in recognising delirium and in a reduction of misdiagnosed delirium. The authors themselves suggest a potential weakness in their reported results due to a time differential between the delivery of the educational content and the assessment of the delirium. This reduces the level of validity that the results appear to highlight.

Other screening tools identified.

Alongside those recommended tools, the literature highlighted a variety of tools which had been developed using the original CAM.

Nu-DESC

Gaudreau et al (2005) in their study explain the Nu-DESC's design, providing clinicians with a scale for delirium rating which is user-friendly and does not take long to complete, but is also reliable and has validity, and suggest Nu-DESC (appendix 17) is within the tools available which fulfil these criteria. Gaudreau et al advice that the development of Nu-DESC from the CAM was because "it had become obvious to us that no existing validated instrument could accurately recognise delirium yet

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remain simple" (2005: 369). Gaudreau et al (2005) explain that the validation of the Nu-DESC was completed in comparison to the existing screening tools in use, which were the CAM and MDAS, and utilising the diagnostic criteria in use at that time, the DSM-III-R and DSM-IV.

Gaudreau et al (2005) explain that during development, the research nurses assessed 52 patients, and no significant deviation between scores performed with the Nu-DESC, MDAS, and CAM was evident (appendix 18). Gaudreau et al suggest these results are "confirming the ability of research nurses to adequately diagnose delirium, with proper training" (2005: 373), specifying that "the Nu-DESC takes the shortest time to complete, on average one minute per patient" (2005: 373).

Hosie et al (2015), in their qualitative study addressing the feasibility of Nu DESC, specifically for them in the setting of inpatient palliative care. They do not provide any qualitative data but do provide themes from the comments of the nurses involved, which advise that in their research, nurses believed this tool was simple to administer, beneficial to recognition of patient deterioration, and only required a short time to complete, and nurses involved were planning to implement the tool into following periods of patient care. This included more experienced nurses who agreed

the Nu-DESC showed enough benefits to warrant inclusion, as it helped bridge any gaps nurses had in their knowledge of delirium. It being shorter may lend benefit to wider use in healthcare, as it may be more feasible for nurses to complete regularly. Hosie et al (2015) explain that many nurses appeared to concur, making comparisons to existing routine screening performed, like NEWS scores. Many of the nurses involved offered the view that their knowledge regarding delirium and its recognition, including the differing types, for example hypoactive, had improved, and that this, in turn, would help boost patient safety and better outcomes.

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Krewulak et al (2021) explain that the Nu-DESC's design allows ease of incorporation into standard daily practice, and while the fluctuating nature of delirium means the score may not provide the complete picture of the patients' condition, it will likely be beneficial, with knowledge of the patients' history, in monitoring for the potential risk of delirium development.

However, of the approaches researched, the Nu-DESC remains one of those with reduced available information in the literature gathered, and it appears to be a tool more sparsely used or known about, with the literature by Ozsaban and Acaroglu (2015) advising the tools use, in only 6.3% of delirium assessments.

Hosie et al (2015), also suggest some limitations to their literature, highlighting that the clinicians involved in the data gathering were aware of the nature of the study, and this may have created a bias where they assessed or expected to find delirium more frequently than would have occurred in standard practice, so causing a deviation in the results. Some participants reported a lack of confidence in the patient scoring method provided for some presentations including psychomotor retardation, and reduced or lack of consciousness, which makes this approach

more complex to implement in clinical areas like ICU. The lack of clarity also makes recognition of delirium increasingly problematic, as it is reliant on the individual nurses' perception of the symptoms and their severity and causality rather than a definitive score providing the answer. Increased staff training on symptoms and presentation of delirium would also be beneficial, as in some cases, where nurses expected to see reductions in consciousness, whether resulting from medication side effects or general drowsiness, they failed to attribute it to a potential delirium symptom. However, as at that point it is not conclusive what is causing the

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symptom, this alone should be classed as a delirium symptom, and the patient should gain increased monitoring.

After previously advising the simple administration, benefit to recognition of deterioration, and a short time to complete, followed by advising of nurses, including more experienced nurses, plans to implement into patient care, Hosie et al explain in their literature the problematic nature of nurses participation compared with their views on their ability to recognise delirium without the use of a tool, with one nurse reported as commenting that the Nu-DESC is “probably a good assessment to have on board, but any nurse worth their salt doesn’t actually need that assessment to work that out” (2015: 3281). Use of a tool not being mandatory, as others like the NEWs are, creates situations where differing perceptions are built of the presentation of a patient, from the opinion of various nurses. This can cause misdiagnosis of other assumed conditions, like dementia, side effects of procedures or medications, or simply missed delirium altogether. This is further substantiated by a quote from Hosie et al of “some participants expressed that ‘good’ nurses did not need the Nu

DESC to recognise when patients were delirious” (2015: 3281). Continuing with “a combination of pride and great confidence in one’s nursing capabilities are potential barriers to implementing the Nu-DESC as a routine screening tool” (2015: 3281).

While it may be true that the nurse in question can recognise delirium, the presence of a screening tool is still preferable to personal perception of delirium, to prevent misplaced pride or knowledge gaps preventing use of the tool, to decrease missed cases, and to have a record of symptom progression, time frame, treatment options, and medical team input. A more complete picture is always of increased benefit.

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Some of the screening tools developed from the CAM, but which had less available literature include, the DI.

The DI is another tool originally derived from the CAM. McCusker et al. say, “The Delirium Index (DI) is an instrument for the measurement of severity of symptoms of delirium that is based solely upon observation of the individual patient, without additional information from family members, nursing staff or the patient’s medical chart.” (2004: 1) (appendix 19). They continue to explain that the CAM areas used to develop the DI include all areas, other than those relating to reduced ability to assess or due to variations in acuteness (appendix 20). Schreier advises “patients are rated by health care provider observation of 0 symptoms to 3 severe symptoms on seven of the CAM domains” (2010: 181).

McCusker et al (2004) advise that when judging the DI for validity, during the validation process, the patient screening group was evaluated using the CAM and SPMSQ, subsequently, they were also assessed using the DI, with the screening

staff blinded to the original results. It was found by McCusker et al that “measures of fluctuation were significantly higher in those with delirium than those without delirium, for patients with and without delirium, respectively” (2004: 1746-1747). McCusker et al (2004) offer the opinion that the reported results are suggestive of the DI being a tool which is both valid and reliable for monitoring delirium severity and provides ease of use, having the ability to provide their monitoring with patient observation alone rather than the need for increased information from other healthcare providers or patient relatives. They explain that the findings suggest that use by a person trained will provide results from the DI which offer a good level of reliability, and that

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this provides the DI with a level of sensitivity allowing its use in hospitalised patients and offering a sensitivity to external factors, including medication. These findings suggest the DI has a beneficial place in delirium severity monitoring for hospitalised patients. However, information on the DI was sparse, with much of the information regarding its use found from the same authors, suggesting its use is either not widely spread or its validity has yet to be established enough for wide-scale usage.

The MDAS.

Ali et al (2011), and Breitbart et al (1997) provide details on the MDAS, and its design to assess the severity of delirium (appendix 21). This is detailed further by Shi et al, who explain the “Memorial delirium assessment scale (MDAS) assesses severity of delirium (2014: 1) they continue with the explanation that MDAS which consists of ten items of assessment (appendix 22), has been found reliable and valid, and as such has been translated into various languages allowing its use across many countries. Miranda et al explain its development, advising it was

“originally designed for patients with advanced cancer and later adapted for use in critically ill patients” (2023: 9).

Shi et al (2014) found the MDAS, compared to results gathered using the CAM, to have a delirium identity accuracy of 97.6%. They do however, highlight potential weaknesses of the MDAS, saying the final item of assessment, namely that of the sleep-wake cycle, only provided a weak correlation, and that during the assessment stage, patients' assessments were not completed on the third postoperative day but were done on days 1, 2 and 4. While these weaknesses may result in reduced symptom recognition and reporting over time, Shi et al offer the opinion “the MDAS has demonstrated good reliability and validity in clinical

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applications, and, has been suggested to not only assess the severity of symptoms of delirium but also to identify delirium” (2014: 5). Gaudreau et al also highlight similar specifications of the MDAS saying “the MDAS is suited for delirium treatment research and severity-rating and not intended for delirium diagnosis, but our study further suggests that it can be used as a diagnostic instrument presenting high sensitivity and specificity” (2005: 373), continuing by advising a 10 minute length of time required to administer the MDAS.

By comparison, Sands et al concluded in their research, “as there were no true positives in MDAS sample, the sensitivity and specificity of the MDAS in relation to SQiD and reference standard (psychiatric interview) could not be statistically assessed in our sample” (2010: 563). Sands et al (2010) highlight that the results they gathered were from a small sample size of only 19 patients, only 15 of which received MDAS scores.

The DRS.

Ramamurthy and Scharre (2022) explain, the DRS is a scale utilising ten factors to identify delirium, which was developed from the CAM and can rate the severity or progression of delirium as well as highlighting its presence initially (appendix 23).

Trzepacz et al (2001), speaking of the DRS, further explain its translation into various languages due to its wide use throughout the healthcare field. They do, however, highlight a limitation in the tool, saying its design is to measure specific behaviours in either hyperactive or hypoactive delirium and the psychomotor behaviours they exhibit, which Trzepacz et al suggest, may result in limitations in its effectiveness in assessing other subtypes of delirium. This triggered them to develop

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the DRS-R-98, a 16-part screening tool, (appendix 24) attempting to bridge the highlighted gaps in the existing tool (appendix 25), which they suggest has been validated as reliable in both diagnostic and severity scales.

The DOSS

Ali et al (2011) advise the DOSS was developed from the CAM using the DSM-IV, and that a score of 3 using DOSS indicates delirium. Neefjes et al (2019) in their study assessing the accuracy of the DOS, explain the adjustment of the DOSS to the DOS to simplify its implementation in clinical settings (appendix 26).

Gavinski, Carnahan and Weckmann, in their validation report, specify, “the Delirium Observation Screening (DOS) Scale is a brief screening tool based on observation” (2016: 1), advising that the scale has been validated in various patient

populations and clinical areas and had been designed to be implemented by nurses on a 12 hourly basis. Neefjes et al (2019) and Schroder Pedersen et al, speaking of validation, advise the DOS (appendix 27) when used on an 8-hourly basis has been shown to have very high levels of validation, specifying its “high specificity (97%) and sensitivity (100%)” (2014: 439). Neefjes et al continue by expressing “the Delirium Observation Scale (DOS) appears to be the most suitable nurse-rated screening instrument”, adding “it can be assessed by nurses without specific training, and is experienced as user-friendly” (2019: 2). This opinion is agreed with by Gavinski, Carnahan and Weckmann, who found “87% of nurses were confident in DOS administration; 92% could complete the DOS in under three minutes; and 79% agreed that performing the DOS is easy” (2016: 3). This view as detailed by Neefjes et al, may be because of the fact “the DOS can be completed by nurses based on the observations made during regular nursing care” (2019: 5).

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Despite this, Schroder Pedersen et al (2014) advise the limitation of the DOS not being designed to measure delirium severity. This may be one of the reasons the nurses Gavinski, Carnahan and Weckmann (2016) surveyed, showed fewer positive results when asked about the value of completing the DOS and its benefit to patient care. Gavinski, Carnahan and Weckmann, felt that potentially “developing guidelines for responding to positive DOS screens and documenting its impact on care may incentivise use” (2016: 4).

And, the RADAR

Speaking about its development from the CAM, Soboh et al advice, “recently Voyer et al. developed a delirium screening tool (RADAR) that can be administered by

nurses as part of their daily routine” (2024: 2). This is agreed with by Fabrizi et al (2024), who offer guidance that it only takes 7 seconds to complete, and they build on this advising this is an increase in speed in comparison to other screening tools.

Voyer et al specify “RADAR was developed with the aim of improving the recognition of delirium by addressing several limitations of current delirium tools, mostly related to their administration time, ease of use, generalisability and validity for clinical practice” (2015: 9).

Fabrizi et al (2024) and Voyer et al (2015) explain the RADAR (appendix 28) as a 3-item scale based on patient observation, which can be completed during routine nursing tasks like medication rounds. This means it is feasible to complete numerous times during a day, allowing optimum monitoring of patients for the development or fluctuation of symptoms of delirium. This gathering of information solely from observation rather than patient interaction is coupled with a lack of need to be aware of the patient’s cognitive baseline.

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Voyer et al (2015) advise that although some training was provided to staff, this was minimal, totalling only 15 minutes.

Fabrizi et al (2024), Voyer et al (2015) and Soboh et al (2024) all offer evidence of the validity and reliability of RADAR, even comparing it with the 4AT (appendix 29).

However, there are noted limitations of RADAR, with Voyer et al (2015) offering the need for patient observation to create a score, and as they advise, this occurs during medication distribution, which significantly lowers the chances of recognising delirium in those patients not requiring medication. Soboh et al also say

“RADAR provides only a partial evaluation of delirium”. Continuing, “as RADAR is not specific for delirium its specificity needs to be improved for its use in clinical practice” (2024: 2).

As well as the variety of tools developed with their base in CAM, are some other tools which have been developed independently from the CAM.

The DEAR

Freter et al (2015) discuss the DEAR and the risk factors used to assess for delirium (appendix 30). Meehan et al build on this by advising “the Delirium Elderly At Risk (DEAR) screening tool was designed to predict the risk of delirium in older surgical patients” (2023: 150).

Haslam-Larmer and Vellani (2024) advise that the DEAR screening tool is a simple, validated assessment used to evaluate delirium risk preoperatively. This is

achieved utilising five key risk factors: advanced age, a history of cognitive impairment, reliance on sensory aids, functional limitations, and chronic use of alcohol or benzodiazepines. Meehan et al (2023) explain these factors were evident in the original criteria (appendix 31). Haslam-Larmer and Vellani (2024) and Freter et al (2005), both highlight the need to have baseline information about the patient, advising relatives to provide information as a vital resource. They continue to explain the empowerment nurses receive when engaging in the investigation or treatment of delirium, utilising these types of screening tools, allowing swift recognition and treatment of delirium. Freter et al (2015) advise on the simplicity of the DEAR and

the high sensitivity and validity of its results (appendix 32), advising its potential to be adopted into routine nursing care.

Freter et al do offer limitations, stating “further research is required to evaluate the DEAR in other orthopaedic populations (e.g. hip fractures), and to design and implement delirium prevention interventions” (2005: 170).

The NEECHAM

Neelon et al 1992, and Matsushita, Matsushima and Maruyama endorse that, the “NEECHAM is widely used by medical staff (excepting psychiatrists) to discriminate delirium from nonconfusional state in a systematic manner” (2004: 158), stating the “NEECHAM was shown to be a scaling tool equal to the task” (2004: 162) (appendix 33).

Having this type of tool to aid in delirium recognition, would be beneficial for nurses and their patients, with Levkoff et al (1991), explaining the development of NEECHAM was with the aim of creating a tool for swift assessment and diagnosis of the cognitive decline associated with delirium, advising of its nine-item scale to rate patients (appendix 34).

Van Rompaey et al (2008), to highlight the comparison between the NEECHAM and the CAM-ICU, suggested that most of the patients scoring positive on the CAM-ICU were also scored as such on the NEECHAM, whereas many of those scoring negative on the CAM-ICU, scored as normal or at risk on the NEECHAM.

To show correlation between these findings and their likely impact on nursing care, Schreier (2010) reported in their pilot study, that only 13% of the nurses involved used the NEECHAM and highlighted a difficulty in incorporating the NEECHAM into existing electronic recording systems.

The literature review also highlighted various other diagnostic Instruments, which are not designed to screen for delirium but can be used alongside validated tools. The other tools routinely mentioned in the research, which it is suggested may aid in delirium detection are.

5P's, PINCHME, CHART-DEL, MMSE, CIWA, GSC, Beck's Depression Inventory, MoCA, Mini-Cog, RASS, HELP, SPMSQ, ADL, ABCDEF Bundle, TDF.

Alongside these, are tools utilised to assess the nurses' knowledge bases and attempt to increase them, including in-service education, often with knowledge transfer, and the undertaking of an NDKA to check the level of knowledge the nurses currently possess. And finally, a vital part of the recognition of change from baseline is information from friends and relatives, who can aid nurses in distinguishing between delirium and dementia by providing the patients' normal baseline.

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Even with the availability of these various tools and methods to help diagnose delirium, Ragheb et al "identify barriers and challenges to delirium screening on inpatient units" (2023: 2) and advise an apparent low sensitivity with current tools. They continue by saying "nurses report negative experiences, often feeling frustrated by challenges surrounding delirium care" (2023: 3). Findings presented by Ragheb et al suggest a negative impact on nurses' mental health with use of delirium tools they

are unfamiliar with, compounded by the fact “delirium is also managed on a unit-by-unit basis without standardized hospital protocols” (2023: 7).

Conclusion

The literature review demonstrated the availability of a range of delirium screening tools. However, it also highlights many nurses appearing comfortable using their own clinical judgement either with or in place of a validated screening tool. With Blevins and Degennaro highlight the “under-recognition of delirium by

health care professionals is an extensive problem: Delirium is estimated to be undetected in 30% to 75% of cases” (2018: 271), and El Hussein, Hirst and Salyers (2015) and Miranda et al (2018) advising that often nurses do not recognise delirium in their patients irrespective of its severity, this puts clinical judgement alone into question.

Delirium is a complex, fluctuating condition that, if not managed, can have a significant impact on the life of the individual, potentially even increasing the risk of death. The literature found during the review highlighted a variety of screening tools used, as well as some tools not designed for delirium, but which can be used beneficially alongside them. Use of these tools alongside nurses’ intuition is the best way to increase recognition. NICE guidelines have three specific screening tools (4AT, CAM-ICU, ICDSC) that they suggest for the detection and monitoring of the symptoms, along with the SQiD, used to trigger the use of the screening process.

Alongside these four, there are various other tools developed by different specific areas, created for screening, but most of them are all based on one of the original tools (CAM), and have been adjusted to attempt to impact speed or accuracy. Other tools designed for different areas of mental capacity assessment can assist nurses during the implementation of the official screening tools but are not specifically designed to assess or monitor delirium themselves.

Alaterre et al (2023), Blevins and Degennaro (2018), and Meghani and Timmins (2024), share the view that delirium screening is an important assessment, which should be undertaken regularly and with specific validated tools following up to-date clinical guidance, saying that any improvement in delirium screening and

subsequent enhancement of nursing knowledge is fundamental to delirium recognition and reduction.

In their research, Blevins and Degennaro found that “although nurses deemed delirium a significant issue, delirium screening was not considered necessary” (2018: 271). In their paper, Scott, McIlveney and Mallice (2013) agree with this opinion, suggesting most nurses believed it should be integrated into daily nursing practice for the enhancement of patient care.

While many of these tools take minimal time and training to complete, and the guidelines advise their use, there is still no official rule advising nurses to complete these on a set basis, and nurses show reluctance to adhere to recommendations either because of time constraints, lack of confidence, the misplaced belief that the symptoms presenting represent part of normal cognitive decline associated with age, dementia, or depression, or the misplaced assumption that their clinical judgement is more beneficial.

There are some limitations to the research conducted during this dissertation which need to be highlighted.

Time to conduct the research and complete the dissertation was a limitation, as this was completed in 5 months while studying other topics full time, attending placement, and working shifts alongside. With more time a more detailed level of understanding may have been possible.

Literature was another limitation, as initially, many abstracts appeared to hold valuable information. However, those papers on occasion were either not available without being purchased or were not available in English. Having access to those

papers may have provided extra information valuable to this piece of work.

Some of the screening tools had minimal information available, or the number of patients and/or nurses involved was small. This makes validating the claims made difficult, as there are minimal numbers for a true comparison.

Finally, author bias may be a factor in some of the literature, as either the authors provided monetary compensation to those involved or the paper was written on a screening tool they had developed and were validating, so they had a personal stake in the results.

Recommendations

While the tools to diagnose and monitor delirium are available, there appear

to be various hurdles to consistent delivery, partially resulting from different tools being used in different trusts, including the use of tools other than those recommended by NICE, or nurses misplaced belief that the symptoms presenting represent part of normal cognitive decline associated with age, dementia, or depression. These are all factors which can impact the validity and effectiveness of the screening performed, and as such, require development.

Instead of individual trusts developing different versions of the tools, and timescales for screening, nurses would benefit from standardised and structured training on the signs of delirium and use of the recommended screening tools as part of mandatory learning. This along with the development of online triggers similar to the NEWS score or Sepsis screening which the symptoms are entered into at set periods of the day, and which flag up potential delirium and trigger protocols to follow and require handing over to the relevant person for review, i.e. physician, may improve the percentage of delirium cases captured and so enable increased monitoring and earlier intervention if required.

While there is clear benefit in the use of clinical judgement alongside screening tools on occasion, it is important to recognise that the use of screening tools should be the gold standard care, with appropriate training alongside to ensure each nurse is at a similar awareness level. Screening tools are then in a good place to try to help capture as many incidents of delirium as possible, where variations in nurses' training or perceptions of symptoms alone may miss them.

Alaterre, C. et al. (2023). Monitoring delirium in the intensive care unit: Diagnostic accuracy of the CAM-ICU tool when performed by certified nursing assistants - A prospective multicenter study. *Intensive & critical care nursing: the official journal of the British Association of Critical Care Nurses*, 79, 103487. Available at: doi.org/10.1016/j.iccn.2023.103487. [Accessed 19 December 2024].

Ali, S. et al. (2011). Insight into delirium. *Innovations in clinical neuroscience*, 8 (10), 25–34. Available at: <https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC3225129/> [Accessed 19 December 2024].

Aveyard, H. and Sharp, P. (2017). *A Beginner's Guide To Evidence Based Practice In Health and Social Care. 3rd Edition*. London, England: Open University Press.

Bergeron, N. et al. (2001). Intensive Care Delirium Screening Checklist: evaluation of a new screening tool. *Intensive care medicine*, 27 (5), 859–864. Available at: [doi10.1007/s001340100909](https://doi.org/10.1007/s001340100909) [Accessed 19 December 2024].

Blevins, C. and DeGennaro, R. (2018). Educational intervention to improve delirium recognition by nurses. *American journal of critical care: an official publication, American Association of Critical-Care Nurses*, 27 (4), 270–278. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.4037/ajcc2018851> [Accessed 19 December 2024].

Breitbart, W. et al. (1997). The Memorial Delirium Assessment Scale. *Journal of pain and symptom management*, 13 (3), 128–137. Available at: [doi:10.1016/S0885-](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0885-)

3924(96)00316-8 [Accessed 19 December 2024].

El Hussein, M., Hirst, S. and Salyers, V. (2015). Factors that contribute to underrecognition of delirium by registered nurses in acute care settings: a scoping review of the literature to explain this phenomenon. *Journal of clinical nursing*, 24 (7– 8), 906–915. Available at: doi:10.1111/jocn.12693 [Accessed 19 December 2024].

Fabrizi, D. et al. (2024). Diagnostic accuracy of the Recognizing Acute Delirium as part of your Routine (RADAR) scale for delirium assessment in hospitalized older adults: A cross-sectional study. *Healthcare (Basel, Switzerland)*, 12 (13), 1294. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.3390/healthcare12131294> [Accessed 19 December 2024].

Fraser, V. et al. (2018). Evaluation of an intervention with nurses for delirium detection after cardiac surgery. *Worldviews on evidence-based nursing*, 15 (1), 38–44. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1111/wvn.12266> [Accessed 19 December 2024].

Freter, S. et al. (2015). Risk of pre-and post-operative delirium and the Delirium Elderly At Risk (DEAR) tool in hip fracture patients. *Canadian geriatrics journal: CGJ*, 18 (4), 212–216. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.5770/cgj.18.185> [Accessed 19 December 2024].

Freter, S. et al. (2005). Predicting post-operative delirium in elective orthopaedic patients: the Delirium Elderly At-Risk (DEAR) instrument. *Age and ageing*, 34 (2),

169–171. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1093/ageing/afh245> [Accessed 19 December 2024].

Gaudreau, J. et al. (2005). Fast, systematic, and continuous delirium assessment in hospitalized patients: the nursing delirium screening scale. *Journal of pain and symptom management*, 29 (4), 368–375. Available at:

doi:10.1016/j.jpainsymman.2004.07.009 [Accessed 19 December 2024].

Gavinski, K., Carnahan, R. and Weckmann, M. (2016). Validation of the delirium observation screening scale in a hospitalized older population. *Journal of hospital medicine: an official publication of the Society of Hospital Medicine*, 11 (7), 494–497. Available at: doi:10.1002/jhm.2580. [Accessed 19 December 2024].

Haslam-Larmer, L. and Vellani, S. (2024). Postoperative delirium in geriatric orthopedic and trauma patients: Care begins preoperatively! *International journal of orthopaedic and trauma nursing*, 56 (101143), 101143. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijotn.2024.101143> [Accessed 19 December 2024].

Hosie, A. et al. (2015). Nurse perceptions of the Nursing Delirium Screening Scale in

two palliative care inpatient units: a focus group study. *Journal of clinical nursing*, 24 (21–22), 3276–3285. Available at: doi: 10.1111/jocn.12925 [Accessed 19 December 2024].

Kalish, V., Gillham, J. and Unwin, B. (2014). Delirium in older persons: evaluation and management. *American family physician*, 90 (3), 150–158. Available at:

- 50 - | Page

<http://www.aafp.org/afp/2014/0801/150-s1.html>. [Accessed 19 December 2024].

Koizia, L. et al. (2019). Delirium after emergency hip surgery - common and serious, but rarely consented for. *World journal of orthopedics*, 10 (6), 228–234. Available at: doi:10.5312/wjo.v10.i6.228 [Accessed 19 December 2024].

Kong, D. et al. (2022). Factors associated with post-operative delirium in hip fracture patients: what should we care. *European journal of medical research*, 27 (1), 40. Available at: doi:10.1186/s40001-022-00660-9 [Accessed 19 December 2024].

Krewulak, K. et al. (2020). The CAM-ICU-7 and ICDSC as measures of delirium severity in critically ill adult patients. *PloS one*, 15 (11), 0242378. Available at: | <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0242378> [Accessed 19 December 2024].

Levkoff, S. et al. (1991). Review of research instruments and techniques used to detect delirium. *International psychogeriatrics*, 3 (2), 253–271. Available at: [https://www.intpsychogeriatrics.org/article/S1041-6102\(24\)03322-2/fulltext](https://www.intpsychogeriatrics.org/article/S1041-6102(24)03322-2/fulltext) [Accessed 19 December 2024].

MacLulich, A. et al. (2019). The 4 'A's test for detecting delirium in acute medical patients: a diagnostic accuracy study. *Health technology assessment (Winchester, England)*, 23 (40), 1–194. Available at: DOI 10.3310/hta23400 [Accessed 19 December 2024].

Marcantonio, E. (2008). Clinical management and prevention of delirium. *Psychiatry*

- 51 - | Page

(Abingdon, England), 7 (1), 42–48. Available at:

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mppsy.2007.11.004> [Accessed 19 December 2024].

Matsushita, T., Matsushima, E. and Maruyama, M. (2004). Early detection of postoperative delirium and confusion in a surgical ward using the NEECHAM confusion scale. *General hospital psychiatry*, 26 (2), 158–163. Available at: doi:10.1016/j.genhosppsy.2003.08.011 [Accessed 19 December 2024].

McCusker, J. et al. (2004). The delirium index, a measure of the severity of delirium: new findings on reliability, validity, and responsiveness: Delirium index. *Journal of the American Geriatrics Society*, 52 (10), 1744–1749. Available at: doi:10.1111/j.1532-5415.2004.52471.x [Accessed 19 December 2024].

Meehan, A. et al. (2023). Development and validation of a delirium risk prediction model using a modified version of the Delirium Elderly at Risk (mDEAR) screen in hospitalized patients aged 65 and older: A medical record review. *Geriatric nursing (New York, N.Y.)*, 51, 150–155. Available at:

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gerinurse.2023.03.003> [Accessed 19 December 2024].

Meghani, S. and Timmins, F. (2024). Intensive care nurses' perceptions and awareness of delirium and delirium prevention guidelines. *Nursing in critical care*, 29 (5), 943–952. Available at: DOI: 10.1111/nicc.13060 [Accessed 19 December 2024].

Miranda, F. et al. (2018). Confusion Assessment Method for the intensive care unit (CAM-ICU) for the diagnosis of delirium in adults in critical care settings. *The*

- 52 - | Page

Cochrane library, 2018 (9), CD013126. Available at: DOI: 10.1002/14651858.CD013126. [Accessed 19 December 2024].

Miranda, F. et al. (2023). Confusion Assessment Method for the Intensive Care Unit (CAM-ICU) for the diagnosis of delirium in adults in critical care settings. *Cochrane database of systematic reviews*, 11 (11), CD013126. Available at: DOI: 10.1002/14651858.CD013126.pub2. [Accessed 19 December 2024].

Mohseni Moallem Kolaei, N., Ayatollahi, H. and Elyasi, F. (2021). Delirium in burn patients: Developing a mobile application for assessment and diagnosis. *Journal of burn care & research: official publication of the American Burn Association*, 42 (1), 87–92. Available at: doi:10.1093/jbcr/iraa122 [Accessed 19 December 2024].

Neefjes, E. et al. (2019). Accuracy of the Delirium Observational Screening Scale (DOS) as a screening tool for delirium in patients with advanced cancer. *BMC cancer*, 19 (1), 160. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12885-019-5351-8>

[Accessed 19 December 2024].

NHS inform (2024). *Delirium*. [Online]. NHS inform. 24th May 2024. Available at: <https://www.nhsinform.scot/illnesses-and-conditions/brain-nerves-and-spinal-cord/delirium/> [Accessed 19 December 2024].

NICE. (2023). *Recommendations | Delirium: prevention, diagnosis and management in hospital and long-term care | Guidance | NICE*. [Online]. National Institute for Health and Care Excellence. 18th January 2023. Available at

<https://www.nice.org.uk/guidance/cg103/chapter/Recommendations> [Accessed 19 December 2024].

- 53 - | Page

Özsaban, A. and Acaroglu, R. (2016). Delirium assessment in intensive care units: practices and perceptions of Turkish nurses. *Nursing in critical care*, 21 (5), 271–278. Available at: doi: 10.1111/nicc.12127 [Accessed 19 December 2024].

Ragheb, J. et al. (2023). Barriers to delirium screening and management during hospital admission: a qualitative analysis of inpatient nursing perspectives. *BMC health services research*, 23 (1), 712. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12913-023-09681-4> [Accessed 19 December 2024].

Rajeev, A., Railton, C. and Devalia, K. (2022). The crucial factors influencing the development and outcomes of postoperative delirium in proximal femur fractures. *Aging medicine*, 5 (2), 94–100. Available at: DOI: 10.1002/agm2.12206 [Accessed

10.1016/j.pmn.2009.07.002 [Accessed 19 December 2024].

Schrøder Pedersen, S. et al. (2014). Effects of a screening and treatment protocol with haloperidol on post-cardiotomy delirium: a prospective cohort study. *Interactive cardiovascular and thoracic surgery*, 18 (4), 438–445. Available at: doi:10.1093/icvts/ivt501 [Accessed 19 December 2024].

Scott, P., McIlveney, F. and Mallice, M. (2013). Implementation of a validated delirium assessment tool in critically ill adults. *Intensive & critical care nursing: the official journal of the British Association of Critical Care Nurses*, 29 (2), 96–102. Available at:

- 55 - | Page

<http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.iccn.2012.09.001> [Accessed 19 December 2024].

Shi, Z. et al. (2014). Using the Chinese version of Memorial Delirium Assessment Scale to describe postoperative delirium after hip surgery. *Frontiers in aging neuroscience*, 6, 297. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.3389/fnagi.2014.00297> [Accessed 19 December 2024].

Soboh, R. et al. (2024). Validation of a viable delirium detection test performed by nurses and physicians during routine patient care. *BMC geriatrics*, 24 (1), 297. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12877-024-04884-8> [Accessed 19 December 2024].

Tieges, Z., Lowrey, J. and MacLulich, A. (2021). What delirium detection tools are used in routine clinical practice in the United Kingdom? Survey results from 91% of

acute healthcare organisations. *European geriatric medicine*, 12 (6), 1293–1298.

Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s41999-021-00507-2> [Accessed 19 December 2024].

Trzepacz, P. et al. (2001). Validation of the Delirium Rating Scale-revised-98:

comparison with the delirium rating scale and the cognitive test for delirium:

Comparison with the delirium rating scale and the cognitive test for delirium. *The journal of neuropsychiatry and clinical neurosciences*, 13 (2), 229–242. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1176/jnp.13.2.229> [Accessed 19 December 2024].

Van Rompaey, B. et al. (2008). A comparison of the CAM-ICU and the NEECHAM

- 56 - | Page

Confusion Scale in intensive care delirium assessment: an observational study in

non-intubated patients. *Critical care (London, England)*, 12 (1), R16. Available at:

<https://doi.org/10.1186/cc6790> [Accessed 19 December 2024].

Varghese, N. et al. (2014). Delirium in older people in hospital: an education

programme. *British journal of nursing (Mark Allen Publishing)*, 23 (13), 704–709.

Available at: <https://doi.org/10.12968/bjon.2014.23.13.704> [Accessed 19 December 2024].

Voyer, P. et al. (2015). Recognizing acute delirium as part of your routine [RADAR]: a validation study. *BMC nursing*, 14 (1), 19. Available at:

<https://doi.org/10.1186/s12912-015-0070-1> [Accessed 19 December 2024].

Appendices

Appendix 1

Table 1 Delirium diagnostic criteria from the Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders (DSM-IV)

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- A. Disturbance of consciousness (i.e., reduced clarity of awareness of the environment) with reduced ability to focus, sustain or shift attention.
 - B. A change in cognition (such as memory deficit, disorientation, language disturbance) or the development of a perceptual disturbance that is not better accounted for by a pre-existing, established, or evolving dementia.
 - C. The disturbance develops over a short period of time (usually hours to days) and tends to fluctuate during the course of the day.
 - D. There is evidence from the history, physical examination, or laboratory findings that the disturbance is caused by the direct physiological consequences of a general medical condition.
-

Bergeron et al 2001

Appendix 2

Table 1. DSM-5 Diagnostic Criteria for Delirium

- A disturbance in attention (i.e., reduced ability to direct, focus, sustain, and shift attention) and awareness (reduced orientation to the environment).
- The disturbance develops over a short period of time (usually hours to a few days), represents a change from baseline attention and awareness, and tends to fluctuate in severity during the course of a day.
- An additional disturbance in cognition (e.g., memory deficit, disorientation, language, visuospatial ability, or perception).
- The disturbances in Criteria A and C are not explained by another preexisting, established, or evolving neurocognitive disorder and do not occur in the context of a severely reduced level of arousal, such as coma.
- There is evidence from the history, physical examination, or laboratory findings that the disturbance is a direct physiological consequence of another medical condition, substance intoxication or withdrawal (i.e., due to a drug of abuse or to a medication), or exposure to a toxin, or is due to multiple etiologies.

*DSM-5 = Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders, 5th ed.
 Reprinted with permission from American Psychiatric Association. Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders, 5th ed. Washington, DC: American Psychiatric Association; ©2013-596. All rights reserved.*

Kalish, Gillham, and Unwin, 2014

Appendix 3

**Table 1.
 Delirium Risk Factors in the Older Adult and Prevention Strategies**

Physiologic Characteristic	Evidence for ↑ Risk	Prevention Strategy
Age	Older age	More frequent assessment
Oxygenation	↓ O ₂ saturation	Monitor oxygen saturation closely, apply oxygen when indicated
Fluid balance	Dehydration	Monitor BUN, creatinine, sodium, glucose I & O
Circulation	Electrolyte imbalance Hypoperfusion	Provide access to oral fluids and/or provide IV fluids Monitor BP and HR
Temperature	↑	Provide appropriate medical interventions Monitor temperature in patients with infections Provide measures to reduce temperature
Substance use	Withdrawal from alcohol, tobacco, or other substances	Assess prehospital use of substances Monitor for withdrawal symptoms Formulate a plan; possible use of nicotine patches; medications to manage withdrawal symptom
Pain	Unrelieved pain	Schedule round-the-clock pain medication administration Assess for effectiveness of pain management protocol Avoid use of meperidine and propofol hydrochloride
Cognition	Dementia	Assess usual routine including ADL, food likes, sleep habits and incorporate whenever possible Provide reassurance by speaking calmly and informing patient about all activities planned before implementation (e.g., vital sign measurements) Provide consistent nursing staff Provide memory cues Involve family in care
Sensation	Hearing and vision losses	Limit number of room changes Provide assistive devices, and alert staff to losses Provide nightlights Use music
Mobility	↓	Reduce television use and extraneous noise Provide ambulation and range of motion Limit use of indwelling urinary catheters
Polypharmacy	Drug interactions	Review medications for necessity, and consider alternative symptom management

Schreier 2010

Appendix 4

Illness	Patient's factors	Environmental/iatrogenic factors
Cardiovascular instability	Cognitive impairment, pre-existing dementia, and depression	Diagnostic procedures and therapeutic interventions
Acid base disorders	Age > 65	Use of restraints
Electrolyte abnormalities		Sensory deprivation: need for hearing aids and glasses
Sepsis		Sleep deprivation
Respiratory distress		
Acute CNS abnormalities		

<http://www.mc.vanderbilt.edu/ocabdelirium/terminology.html>

Table 1. Factors that have been associated with delirium.

Satyapriya et al 2016

Appendix 5

1.3 Indicators of delirium: at presentation

1.3.1 At presentation, assess people at risk for recent (within hours or days) changes or fluctuations that may indicate delirium. These may be reported by the person at risk, or a carer or relative. These changes may affect:

- cognitive function: for example, worsened concentration, slow responses, confusion
- perception: for example, visual or auditory hallucinations
- physical function: for example, reduced mobility, reduced movement, restlessness, agitation, changes in appetite, sleep disturbance
- social behaviour: for example, difficulty engaging with or following requests, withdrawal, or alterations in communication, mood and/or attitude.

If any of these changes are present, the person should have an assessment (see [recommendation 1.6.1](#)). [2010, amended 2023]

1.3.2 Be particularly vigilant for changes that may indicate [hypoactive delirium](#), which are often missed, such as withdrawal, slow responses, reduced mobility and movement, worsened concentration and reduced appetite. [2010]

NICE 2023

Appendix 6

some simple tools like the Single Question to Identify Delirium (SQID) might be useful to help practitioners notice any changes.

1.6 Assessment and diagnosis

- 1.6.1 If indicators of delirium are identified, a [health or social care practitioner](#) who is competent to do so should carry out an assessment using the 4AT. In critical care or in the recovery room after surgery use the Confusion Assessment Method for the Intensive Care Unit (CAM-ICU) or Intensive Care Delirium Screening Checklist (ICDSC) instead of the 4AT. **[2023]**
- 1.6.2 If the assessment described in recommendation 1.6.1 indicates delirium, a [healthcare professional](#) with the relevant expertise should make the final diagnosis. This could be the same person who made the assessment. **[2023]**
- 1.6.3 If there is difficulty distinguishing between the diagnoses of delirium, dementia or delirium superimposed on dementia, manage the delirium first. **[2010]**
- 1.6.4 Ensure that the diagnosis of delirium is documented both in the person's record or notes, and in their primary care health record. **[2010]**

NICE 2023

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Appendix 10

Instrument	Single Question in Delirium
	<small>NOTE: This card is populated with information from the instrument's original validation study only.</small>
Acronym	SQID
Primary use	Delirium Screening
Area assessed (Number of questions)	Single question: "Do you feel that [patient's name] has been more confused lately?"
Description	A tool for early recognition of delirium to be asked of patient's friends or relatives on a regular basis. SQID was designed as a single item tool to be incorporated into the routine medical history obtained by clinical staff. Since SQID can be assessed regularly, clinical staff can monitor potential changes in condition, and moved to a longer delirium assessment test for confirmation as appropriate.
Versions	1
Scoring information	Single item is rated positive or negative; score trends can be monitored over the course of several days
Cognitive testing	None included or necessary
Estimated time to rate	<1 min
Require trained rater	No
Administer to	Patient's relative or friend
How to obtain	Additional information available: https://doi.org/10.1177/0269216310371556 (Note: article may be behind paywall)
Licensing Fee*	None
Languages available	English
Highest COSMIN** rating	In progress
Test Performance Characteristics	<p>Sands 2010</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Sensitivity (compared to psychiatric interview 0.83 [95% CI 0.28-0.99], Confusion Assessment Method [CAM] 0.67 [0.34-0.92], Mini-Mental State Examination [MMSE] 0.50 [0.13-0.99]) •Specificity (compared to psychiatric interview 0.71 [95% CI 0.42-0.92], CAM 0.67 [0.38-0.88], MDAS 0.64 [0.35-0.87], MMSE 0.59 [0.33-0.82]) •Positive predictive value (compared to psychiatric interview 0.50 [95% CI 0.16-0.84], CAM 0.29 [0.04-0.71], MMSE 0.13 [0.00-0.53]) •Negative predictive value (compared to psychiatric interview 0.91 [95% CI 0.59-1.00], CAM 0.91 [0.59-1.00], MDAS 0.90 [0.56-1.00], MMSE 0.91 [0.59-1.00]) •Agreement with psychiatric interview kappa=0.43 (p=0.023)

* Fees and licensing information is effective as of 2024, but is subject to change over time.

** COSMIN is used to rate a study's evaluation of a survey or test's measurement properties. COSMIN does NOT rate the instrument itself, but helps readers understand if they can have confidence in the results of studies evaluating measurement properties of surveys and tests. For example, a rigorous study evaluating a test with poor measurement properties will receive a "good" COSMIN rating, while a poorly conducted study evaluating a test with good measurement properties will receive a "poor" COSMIN rating. Small sample sizes can impact all COSMIN ratings. You must consider both the COSMIN rating and the results of studies provided when forming your opinion about that test. COSMIN ratings shown are based solely on the instrument's original validation study.

Reference:

Sands, M.B., Darboc, B.P., Harbison, A., Ryan C.J., Lujic, S. (2010). Single Question in Delirium (SQID): testing its efficacy against psychiatric interview, the Confusion Assessment Method and the Memorial Delirium Assessment Scale. *Palliative Medicine*, 24(5):541-545. doi:10.1177/0269216310371556

Sands et al 2010

Appendix 11

Table 3. Comparison of screening tools and SQID vs. psychiatric interview (9)

Comparison		Agreement	Sensitivity	Specificity	PPV	NPV
Psychiatric interview vs	SQID	74%	80%	71%	58%	91%
			(18.36–99.49%)	(41.90–91.61%)	(15.70–84.30%)	(58.72–99.77%)
	CAM	78%	40%	92%	67%	80%
			(5.27–85.24%)	(62.97–99.81%)	(9.43–99.16%)	(51.91–95.67%)
SQID vs.	FDAS	73%	ND	92%	ND	79%
				(61.52–99.79%)		(49.20–95.24%)
	PMSE	74%	20%	92%	58%	76%
			(0.51–71.64%)	(66.13–99.82%)	(1.26–98.74%)	(50.10–93.19%)
SQID vs.	CAM	67%	67%	67%	29	91%
			(9.43–9.16%)	(38.38–88.18%)	(2.67–33.96%)	(58.72–99.77%)
	FDAS	60%	ND	64%	ND ^a	90%
			(0–95%)	(31.14–87.24%)	(0–45.07%)	(51.50–99.35%)
SQID vs.	PMSE	58%	50%	39%	13%	91%
			(1.26–98.74%)	(32.92–81.56%)	(0.32–52.63%)	(58.72–99.77%)

CAM, Confusion Assessment Method; FDAS, Frontal Dementia Assessment Scale; PMSE, Mini-Mental State Examination; SQID, Single Question in Dementia.

NOTE: Some percentages are based on only a small number of cases. Confidence levels are wide. ND is not detectable as there were no true positives in FDAS samples.

Sands et al 2012

Appendix 12

Rajeev, Railton and Devalia 2022

Appendix 13

Miranda et al 2018

Appendix 14

Van Rompaey et al 2008

Appendix 15

Scott, McIlveney and Mallice 2013

Appendix 16

Fraser et al 2018

Appendix 17

Gaudreau et al 2005

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Appendix 18

Gaudreau et al 2005

Appendix 19

McCusker et al. 2004

Appendix 20

McCusker et al. 2004

Appendix 21

Breitbart et al 1997

Breitbart et al 1997

Appendix 23

Ramamurthy and Scharre 2022

Appendix 24

Trzepacz et al 2001

Trzepacz et al 2001

Appendix 26

Neefjes et al 2019

Appendix 27

Schroder Pedersen et al 2014

Appendix 28

Voyer et al 2015

Appendix 29

Soboh et al 2024

Appendix 30

Freter et al 2015

Appendix 31

Meehan et al 2023

Appendix 32

Freter et al 2015

Appendix 33

Matsushita, Matsushima, and Maruyama 2004

Appendix 34

Levkoff et al 1991